

**MISREPRESENTATION OF ZAKĀT AS SADAQAT AMONG MUSLIMS IN
OGUN STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The position of Zakāt and its significance in Islam cannot be undermined. Allah [SWT] in His wisdom and mercy established it for the wealthy believers to purify their wealth and to do social service in the society. This also leads to the even distribution of wealth and the gradual reduction of poverty in Muslim communities around the world. This paper examined the misrepresentation of Zakāt as Ṣadaqat among Muslims in Ogun State. Interviews were conducted to elicit responses from both the distributors and beneficiaries of Zakāt in Ogun State on some major issues like whether the distributors had the basic knowledge of Zakāt and how they distinguish it from ṣadaqat; and whether the beneficiaries were conscious of what they received as Zakāt or ṣadaqat. The work was also interested in understanding where the wealthy distributors of Zakāt acquired their basic knowledge about the annual niṣāb of Zakāt and the processes of understanding the procedure that they needed to follow before finally distributing their annual Zakāt. The paper recommended appropriate orientation for both Zakāt collecting agencies and beneficiaries for them to be Islamically guided on what zakat and sadaqah entailed.

Keywords: Zakāt, Ṣadaqat, Misrepresentation.

Introduction

In the context of working towards reducing poverty not only within the Muslim community but in the entire humanity, Islam has established a tool or mechanism of putting a smile on the face of the less privileged which is called Zakāt. This is one of the fundamentals of Islam, primarily established to ensure the even distribution of Allāh's provisions among mankind. It has been deliberate legislation from Allah (SWT), as He predestined that, wealth shall never go round equally; hence, provided for some than others: "And Allah has favored some of you over others in provision..." (Q16V71)

The aforementioned called for legislation of Zakāt, so there can be a bond of friendship, brotherhood and unity between the rich and the poor. It is also to demonstrate Allāh's directive: "Let a man of wealth spend from his wealth, and he whose provision is restricted, let him spend from what Allah has given him..." (Q65V7). The verse has technically legalized Zakāt for the large wealthy individuals and Ṣadaqat for the small earning people.

Many Islamic organized communities in the world are aware of the differences between Zakāt and Ṣadaqat. According to Akanni (2006), ideal Islamic countries like Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, Libya, Sudan, Bahrain, Bangladesh and the like, appoint bodies or agencies that work purposely for Zakāt and Ṣadaqat administration and management. Daniel Liberto (2002) added that those who fail to pay Zakat in these countries are treated like tax evaders. In such an environment, Zakāt and Ṣadaqat are strictly state affairs, where the government monitors the collection and disbursement to the needy and other categories according to Shari'ah. Malaysian government legislates a penalty of up to three months in jail, a 1,800 pound fine and six strokes of cane for not paying Zakāt.

On the other side of the world like Nigeria in which Ogun State is one of the political entities, Zakāt or Ṣadaqat is more or less a personal religious interest. The administration of Zakāt is only managed voluntarily by Islamic organizations. They take charge of enlightening Muslim adherents on the legality and spirituality of Zakāt. This situation has been a major hindrance to the smooth running of the Zakāt administration among the Muslims of the state. Many are ignorant of the significance of Zakāt and the benefits to be derived by the entire Muslim communities from it. Furthermore, few of the well-meaning Muslims appropriately pay Zakāt while a large number of them misrepresent it with Ṣadaqat deliberately, ignorantly, or due to lack of adequate guidance.

The fact that Zakāt payment is an Islamic religious tax and not alms-giving is yet to be adequately understood by many Muslims in the State. Therefore, an efficient and effective sensitization is needed for the entire Muslim 'Ummah in Ogun State, to promote awareness of Zakāt and distinguish it from Ṣadaqat.

This paper is purposefully working towards: (i) studying the level of awareness about Zakāt among the Muslims of Ogun State; (ii) carrying out research on how Muslims can distinguish Zakāt from Ṣadaqat; (iii) assessing the roles played by the Muslim scholars and clerics in sensitizing the Muslim populace on the significance and appropriate payment of Zakāt; and (iv) proffering suggestions towards ensuring effective and efficient Zakāt compliance among Muslims in Ogun State.

Zakāt: Definition and Essence in Islam

Zakāt is from the word Zakawa which signifies increase or purification. The root meaning of Zakāt comes from the Arabic verb 'Zakiya' (he purified) which goes along with the verse of the Qur'ān that reminds us of the significance of purifying the soul:

And (by) the soul and He who proportioned it. And inspired it (with discernment of) its wickedness and its righteousness. He has succeeded who purifies it. And he has failed who instils it (with corruption) (Q91:7-10).

The above verse teaches that every believer is expected to purify his or her soul with righteous thoughts and actions, to achieve divine success.

Technically, Zakāt is defined to be a poor due, welfare tax, or purifying due. It is known as a compulsory alms-giving and the third pillar of Islam. Zakāt has been put in place by Allāh, for the believers who must have purified their soul to also purify their wealth. This is the reason behind Allāh's commandment to the Prophet to take a portion from the

wealth of the *Ṣaḥābah* as charity: "Take alms from their wealth to purify them and sanctify them with it and invoke Allāh for them..." (Q9:103). Payment of Zakāt is also a recommended and righteous act that does not only purify but also increase wealth:

And whatever you give for interest to increase within the wealth of people will not increase with Allāh. But what you give in Zakāh, desiring the countenance of Allāh – those are the multipliers. (Q30V39)

Zakāt is compulsory for every Muslim Faithful whose wealth must have attained a certain amount called *niṣāb* at a particular time of the year. It is to be paid once a year, or at harvest time in case of crops, or on livestock, or merchandise items. In another scholarly definition by Chapra (1980), Zakāt is a social self-help measure adopted with full religious backing to support the poor and destitute, who are unable to help themselves to eliminate misery and poverty from Muslim society. Adebayo (2011) also in his view posits that "Zakāt is a social insurance fund against unforeseeable calamities that can lead to unexpected and sudden poverty."

Zakāt is compulsory for any eligible Muslim because it is an essential part of worship in Islam through which wealth or properties are purified from corruption. Allah (SWT) deliberately made Zakāt next to *Ṣalāt* in the principles of Islam, because as *Ṣalāt* purifies the soul, Zakāt purifies the wealth. This clears the reason for mentioning *Ṣalāt* and Zakāt together in 82 places in the Qur'an. The position of Zakāt in Islam signifies that anyone who deliberately ignores to pay it has committed apostasy. This quite justified why Abu Bakr waged war against some Muslims who decided not to pay Zakāt after the death of Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

Islam established the institution of Zakāt to create equal opportunities for mankind towards well-being and meaningful livelihood so that wealth will not be controlled by a few people. In outlining the benefits of Zakāt, Chapra (1980) mentions some of them that are essential to societal economic growth and prosperity; poverty eradication, social and economic justice, stability in the real value of money, and equitable distribution of income and wealth, among others.

Zakāt and Ṣadaqat: Similarities and Differences

At times, Zakāt and Ṣadaqat are used interchangeably by scholars. This is because both refer to the act of giving to the have-nots or an act of kindness to others which is done for the sake of Allah without selfish motives. In other words, both are acts of 'Charity'.

Meanwhile, Zakāt is compulsory. It is fixed in amount and to be paid once at a fixed time annually. It is paid by wealthy Muslims on specific items (e.g., money, gold, silver, merchandise materials, farm produce, or livestock) and in totality, Zakāt comes third in position among the pillars of Islam. Ibn 'Abbas (R.A) reported thus; "The Prophet (SAW) sent Mu'ādh to Yemen and said:

Invite them to bear witness that there is no God but Allah and that I am the Messenger of Allah; if they accept this, tell them that Allah has made obligatory on them five prayers every day and night; if they accept this, tell them Allah has made compulsory in their wealth a charity which is

taken from the wealthy among them and given to the poor among them.... (Sahih Bukhari and Muslim)

Ṣadaqah is voluntary with no fixed amount and could be paid at any time and as many as possible times. It could be cash or kind with no specific item. It could be paid by any category of person and not a pillar of Islam. Despite the differences between Zakāt and Ṣadaqah, both are received by the same categories of people.

The people to receive Zakāt are explicitly stated, even though Allāh used the word Ṣadaqat in the Qur'ān.

Charity is only for the persons in poverty and the needy, those who collect them, and those whose hearts are to be reconciled, and to free the captives, and those in debt, and for the way of Allah, and the wayfarers, a duty imposed by Allah, Allah is Knower, Wise (Q9:60).

The above verse is very clear with no ambiguity on the meaning of its content. The people in poverty and the needy are the most destitute in the community and must be cared for. In a properly organized Islamic State, community, or organisation, Zakāt is assessed, collected, and distributed by the appointed agency. Those who are appointed as collectors are also included to receive a reward for their services. This is also an indication that Zakāt should be collected and distributed as public money under the directive of the head of the state, community, or appointed agency with the advice of an expert scholar of an Islamic organization. A new convert is also entitled, to relieve him or her of any immediate problem faced after coming to Islam. In the days of slavery, Zakāt was allowed to be used in paying for ransom. Anyone in debt could also be given Zakāt to settle it. Activities to cater to all categories of humanitarian services could be funded with Zakāt (e.g., provision of hospitals, borehole or pipe bone water, schools, mosques, vocational or human development centers, orphanages or old age homes and empowerment). A stranded traveler is to be assisted with money or materials collected through Zakāt.

Conditions for Zakāt

- a) The payer must be a Muslim. A non-Muslim is not eligible to pay *Zakāt*.
- b) *Zakāt* payer must have attained maturity and puberty age. Some scholars are of opinion that, a minor is not expected to give *Zakāt* from his or her wealth, since he or she cannot perform *Ṣalāt* validly. However, a reasonable number of scholars agree that, pending the matured age to release such wealth, his or her guardian is to pay *Zakāt* on his or her behalf, once it is up to *niṣāb*, according to Q4V6. The legislation was put in place to protect the property from mismanagement and also keep the wealth of the Muslim nation circulating.
- c) Only a sane person is expected to pay *Zakāt*. An insane person is not obligated to pay since he is not liable to perform religious duties and not accountable for his misdeeds. But as gathered by Ambali (2006), the person who looks after his property is expected to help pay *Zakāt* on his behalf while failure to do that lies on the caretaker.

- d) The payer should be a free person not a slave. Whatever owned by a slave belongs to his or her master.
 - e) The recipient must be person in poverty or needy.
 - f) The payer of *Zakāt* must physically be the owner of the item from which *Zakāt* is to be paid, except for the guardian of a minor or caretaker of an insane person's property.
 - g) The property from which *Zakāt* will be paid must be in existence for a round calendar year, except for farm produce that has peculiar season of harvest. The Qur'an explicitly mentions this: "...Eat of (each of) its fruit when it yields and give its due (*Zakāh*) on the day of its harvest..." (Q6:141).
 - h) The recipient must own a wealth or property that reaches the *niṣāb*.
 - i) The recipient must not belong to one's immediate family.
- All the above are in accordance with *Sunnah* and popular opinion among the scholars.

Calculation of Zakāt

Calculation of *Zakāt* is based on *niṣāb* which happens to be the minimum measurement or amount for payment. In other words, *niṣāb* is the technical word that refers to the minimum amount of wealth and possessions that a Muslim must own before being obligated to pay *Zakāt*.

Zakāt calculation is an extremely magnificent administration that will encourage the user to know the correct measure of *Zakāt*. It makes us acquainted with the distribution of *Zakāt* and the rightful receivers. It is generally ordained that 2.5% has been prescribed to be paid as *Zakāt* once the wealth is in our possession reaches or above *niṣāb*. The *niṣāb* varies from one period to another, due to gold or silver value and monetary fluctuation. This is also in accordance with Ambali's view that calculation should be *niṣāb* equivalent of banknotes such as Naira, Riyal, Pound Sterling, and Dollars among others. In the Nigerian context, the equivalent of the Naira to Dollar exchange rate about the monetary value of silver and gold determines the value of *niṣāb* at any given time of the year.

According to the research carried out by Muslim Aid, an International Islamic Organization serving humanity, the year 2022 *niṣāb* for *Zakāt* on silver is valued to be 612.36grams (324.98 pounds) and that of gold is 87.48gram (3,903.52 pounds). From another body called Islamic Relief Worldwide, the silver and gold values as above as of 1st April 2022 were calculated to be 373.54 pounds and 4,144.80 pounds respectively, equivalent to 20 pieces of Dinār with the recommendation of the Prophet (SAW) as reported in *Ṣaḥīḥ fiqhus-Sunnah*. The Society for the Propagation of Islam in Nigeria followed the above and released that, the minimum *niṣāb* upon which 2.5% is payable as *Zakāt* in the year 1443AH is #1,910,179.65k while another organization, the Society for *Zakāt* Professionals as at Sha'bān of 1443AH released #1,837,680.00k to be the minimum. According to Adeyemo (2023), (interviewed, March 24, 2023), he made it known that for Ramadan 1444AH (2023), NAZAS calculated *niṣāb* to be #2,471,501.65k, while that of *Zakāt* and Ṣadaqat Foundation was lesser.

In a nutshell, anyone paying *Zakāt* should use a calculator for gold, silver, cash, and other assets to determine his or her overall wealth; and from there work out how much to

pay as Zakāt. However, debts currently outstanding, including any form of loan are ineligible for Zakāt, so they must be deducted from the overall total.

When calculating total wealth at a time of the year, one must consider the following as items on which *Zakāt* is to be paid:

- (i) the value of gold and silver items owned;
- (ii) money in the bank and cash at home;
- (iii) loans that have been given out;
- (iv) pensions, stocks, shares and investments;
- (v) properties owned as investments (not the one we are living in); and
- (vi) farm and agricultural produce.

For the benefit of the salary earners, contemporary scholars have devised four steps to fulfil the calculation and payment of *Zakāt*:

- i. work out what you own;
- ii. deduct what you owe (any debt); check the balance if it reaches or above the *niṣāb*, because if personal wealth is below the *niṣāb* during one lunar year, no *Zakāt* is owed for that year; and
- iii. Calculate 2.5% across the year.

Zakāt Administration: A Misrepresentation as Ṣadaqat in Ogun State

Ogun State, founded on the 3rd of February 1976 is a typical Yoruba-speaking political entity with a 16,981 km² area in South-western Nigeria and ranked 24th largest among the 36 states in the country. The state was created from the old Western Region of Nigeria and made up of the Egba in the central, wherein the capital city Abeokuta is situated, Yewa/Awori in the west and Ijebu/Remo in the east of the State. These three divisions also make up the three State's Senatorial Districts. The State, according to the last census count in 2006, had a population of 3,751,140 and ranked 16 of the 36 states. Geographically, the state shares borders with Lagos State in the south, Oyo and Osun States in the north, Ondo State in the east and the Republic of Benin in the west. The geographical position of the state led to its title as "Gateway to Nigeria". The State is known for excellence in education, multi-religious communion, tourism, industrialization, viable mineral resources and agricultural advantages.

The Islamic affairs and matters concerning the Muslims in Ogun State are managed by the State Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs, League of Imams and Alfas Ogun State, National Council of Muslim Youth Organization (NACOMYO) and Federation of Muslim Women's Association of Nigeria (FOMWAN).

It is noteworthy to submit that, the above-mentioned Islamic bodies serve as an umbrella for all Islamic organizations in the State, due to their nearness and recognition from the State Government. They serve as advisory bodies to the Government on any matter that concerns Islam and Muslims in the State. Each of these Muslim bodies has committees for different Islamic programs like moon sighting, Hajj Affairs, and Zakāt collection and distribution, among other relevant functions that mainly concern Islam. For effective and efficient performance, these organizations have representatives from districts who also step the functions down to the local levels.

According to an interview, Adeleye (2022) confirms that the majority of the viable Islamic organizations in Ogun State have Zakāt and Ṣadaqat units, yet not functioning optimally. From another end, one such unit is NAṢFAT Agency for Zakāt and Ṣadaqat (NAZAS), Ogun State situated at NAṢFAT mosque, Ijemo Abeokuta under the directive of its headquarters Office in Lagos. This agency collects Zakāt not only from members of NAṢFAT but also from other well-meaning Muslims and assists them in distributing it to the appropriate quarters. Naṣrul-lahi-l-Fātiḥ Society (NAṢFAT) has the advantage of getting meaningful responses for Zakāt and Ṣadaqat from time to time, due to regular enlightenment presentations on Zakāt and Ṣadaqat to its members, at least once in a month during its prayer (Aṣalātu) sessions. NAZAS periodically makes use of two periods of the year, every first month of the Islamic Calendar (Muḥarram) and Ramadan to distribute Zakāt. (Interview with T. Agboola, November 17, 2022)

Some other organizations like Sa'adatu Abadiyat Muslim Organization, Nawair-ud-Deen Society of Nigeria, Ansar-ud-Deen Society, Da'wah Front, The Muslim Congress (TMC), Fatiḥu Qareeb Islamic Organization, to mention but a few also have their Zakāt and Ṣadaqat Unit. Out of them all, it is only NAṢFAT that stands out in terms of frequent enlightenment about Zakāt and Ṣadaqah to her congregation as one of the policies of the Society. (Interview with A. A Adeleye, December 24, 2022).

Zakāt and Ṣadaqat Foundation is another organization that is doing well in Zakāt and Ṣadaqat concerning the distribution and her weekly programme every Sunday evening on one of the Radio Stations in Abeokuta. Her main focus is enlightenment, collection, and disbursement of Zakāt but yet to cover the whole State. This foundation's major challenge is limited resources, especially a lack of adequate funds. It was gathered that the radio program was initially one hour before being reduced to thirty minutes due to insufficient funds. (A. A. Adeleye, December 24, 2022)

Ashafa (2020) further identifies some major frontiers of Zakat distribution organizations in Ogun State; Zakāt and Ṣadaqah Foundation established in the year 2000, Ar-Rahmah Zakāt Foundation founded in 2009, As-Salam Development Foundation, created in 1999 and the Al-Hayat Relief Foundation founded in 1997 but registered in 2006, all in Ijebu-Ode. It is incumbent to emphasize as earlier mentioned that, the NAṢFAT Agency for Zakāt and Ṣadaqat (NAZAS) of Naṣrullah-il-Fātiḥ Society was founded in 2014, with its Ogun State office in Abeokuta came on board in 2016, as Zonal Office that coordinates Zakāt and Ṣadaqat Committees of all branches in the State. According to a report gathered from Ijebu land in the eastern part of Ogun State, two major bodies focus on the collection and administration of Zakāt distribution, namely; Zakāt and Ṣadaqat Foundation and Omo-Owo Islamic Foundation. (S. Wakeel, interviewed on April 23, 2023). It is also discovered that the League of Imams and Alfas of Ijebu and Remo Districts does not have a special committee for Zakāt. This body gathers Ṣadaqat in terms of donations from well-meaning Muslims, who just feel like dashing out of their wealth in the Muslim community. This mostly comes up during the Ramaḍān period and ignorantly tags it as Zakāt. (N. Shittu, interviewed on December 1, 2022)

Furthermore, the report made it known that the Federation of Muslim Women's Association of Nigeria (FOMWAN) Ogun State Chapter is yet to put the administration of Zakāt in operation because the association is an umbrella for women of various

Muslim Organizations. Therefore, the majority of its members are loyal to their organization at the state level. Meanwhile, some well-to-do FOMWAN members pay their Zakāt to the association's Zakāt and Ṣadaqah Committee at the national level. (T. Oderinde, interviewed on November 16, 2022)

From the Ota-Awori Muslim Community of Ogun West District, it is discovered that they are yet to have a formidable Islamic platform for the collection and administration of Zakāt. According to Ibrahim-Aladi (Interviewed on November 6, 2022), most of the new-generation mosques in this community are just encouraging their congregation but the enlightenment they are passing to their members is not enough for them to accept paying Zakāt in the real sense. A large number of Muslims in Ota and its environs are not Zakāt compliant, except a few who belong to some Muslim organizations in Lagos where they are fed with its comprehensive meaning and significance, not only in Islam but also entire humanity. (R. Deinde, interviewed on November 15, 2022)

The act of giving *Ṣadaqatul Fitr* at the end of Ramadan is so common in the Yewa and Awori of Ogun West district. Most of them in this district monetize their *Ṣadaqatul Fitr* and ignorantly regard it as Zakāt. (S. Ibrahim-Aladi, interviewed on November 6, 2022) This paper views that, it may be the fault of their immediate Muslim Scholars and Imams who do not give them enough information or as a result of deliberate personal desire of these half-baked Muslims.

It has been a little bit fair in Ogun Central, especially within Abeokuta where several distributions of Zakāt were done by the League of Imams and Alfas, after being collected from some well-meaning Muslims. M. Soyinka (Interviewed on November 18, 2022) reports that this has been criticized by a set of scholars in the same axis that it has never been Zakāt per se, due to the claims that the monies distributed to the beneficiaries are not substantial enough to be categorized as Zakāt but Ṣadaqat because this has never achieved the purpose of poverty alleviation. They based this on the observation that the same set of people will still come back to beg again because the one given was just meagre and cannot sustain them for a living. There was another report that distributors of Zakāt hold on to the larger percentage of the money that is supposed to be shared with the poor people. (A. A. Adeleye, interviewed on December 24, 2022) This work regards such self-centred attitudes as illegal and not encouraged in Islam, despite they are also part of direct beneficiaries according to Q9:60.

It is noted that the common act of many of the well-to-do Muslims in all parts of Ogun State is an attitude of distributing enveloped money at certain Islamic events like Mawlid Nabiy, Lailatul Qadr, Ramaḍan lectures, 'eid prayers or Hijrah celebrations; gifts to people for answering questions on radio and television and the likes. They claim this to be their Zakāt but never served the intent of Islam for humanity.

This work also gathered that some notable Islamic organizations were working towards making the collection of Zakāt effective in some parts of the state, yet, they were faced with constraints of requests being more than what is on the ground. Some who could not afford to meet up with Islamic standards as far as Zakāt is concerned, therefore, turn it to the distribution of Ṣadaqat. (T. Oderinde, interviewed November 16, 2022) This work confirmed the report of Ashafa (2020) that most of the organizations only work on

monetary Zakāt while other aspects like properties, merchandise items and farm produce are yet to be reckoned with in the collection and distribution of Zakāt.

It is not an understatement to declare that, these organizations utilize all available strategies of technical and human efforts to canvas their eligible Zakāt payers to the extent of having Zakāt and Şadaqat marketing employees to meet their target. However, the major problem of these organizations is their inability to know the worth of their Zakāt payers, before collecting what is to be paid as Zakāt from their wealth. As gathered from T. Oderinde (Interviewed on November 16, 2022), there has never been any interview for the payers before they pay any amount from them, mostly through money transfer into the organizations' bank accounts.

In another report gathered by Ashafa (2020), the majority of those who pay Zakāt in Southwest Nigeria which Ogun State belongs, do not disclose the worth of their wealth and do not accept any evaluation, but just pay according to their idea. The report above has been accepted as this research also found that many of the Muslim philanthropists in Ogun State are fond of earmarking any amount as their annual Zakāt, without consulting Zakāt technical experts. This means that many of the payments claimed to be Zakāt may not have been the actual 2.5% recommended. (M. Soyinka, interviewed on November 18, 2022)

The above is the common attitude of businessmen and farmers among the Muslims in Ogun State who are ignorant of the rate and actual amount of what is to be given out as Zakāt from their merchandised items and farm produce respectively. During our field research, we found that over seventy percent (70%) of the Muslim farmers in the State are not aware of how to pay Zakāt. They only believe in giving out whatever they desire to the less privileged around them after harvesting or at a particular time like Ramadan and other festive periods. (A. A Adeleye, interviewed on December 24, 2022) This can only be categorized as Şadaqat by the standard.

This work found that out of all Islamic organizations that claim to be *Zakāt* sensitizers, collectors and disbursers in Ogun State, only two have records of at least between four to five years and they are; *Zakat* and *Sadaqat* Foundation and NASFAT Agency for *Zakat* and *Sadaqat* (NAZAS).

***Zakāt* and *Şadaqat* Foundation Ogun State Record 2016-2023**

***Zakāt* Collection and Disbursement**

S/N	YEAR	ZAKAT GENERATED	ZAKAT DISBURSED
1	2016		
2	2017		4,930,000
3	2019		4,028,085
4	2020	10,509,399	7,882,313
5	2021	18,957,122	16,687,015
6	2022	21,086,942	18,712,488.65
7	2023	14,514,992 (Egba/Yewa only, Excluding Ijebu/Remo) Ongoing	NOT YET

Source: Office of *Zakāt* and *Şadaqat* Foundation, Ogun State

NAZAS Ogun Zone Collections

	2022	2021	2020	2019
Zakat	381,170	879,420	321,390	559,885
Sadaqat	159,700	370,045	611,625	591,340
Total	540,870	1,249,465	933,015	1,151,225

Source: NASFAT Agency for *Zakāt* and *Ṣadaqat* (NAZAS) Head Office.

From the above tables, one can vividly deduce that the Zakat and Sadaqat Foundation in Ogun State has no clear record for the first three years of existence, that is 2016 to 2019 with disbursement in 2017 and 2019. According to the official in charge, previous officials did not have a definite record till his tenure in 2020. However, the record shows an improvement in the collection and disbursement of Zakat as the collection for 2023 is yet to be completed during the fieldwork of this research.

The record from NAZAS is also similar to the one presented by the Zakat and Sadaqat Foundation in the area of progression. It is glaring from the NAZAS record that gradually, Sadaqat dropped from #591,340 to #159,700, yet the payment of Zakat was not as encouraging in 2022 as it was in the years 2019 and 2021. An officer of the organization tagged the low payment to economic recession in the country but affirmed that, as shown in the record, people are more enlightened about the differences between Zakat and Sadaqat, and prefer the former over the latter due to its position as one of the core pillars of Islam.

In a nutshell, the two records gathered showcase the level of knowledge about differentiating Zakat from Sadaqat in Ogun State. It also implies that there is room for improvement if widespread enlightenment takes place.

Recommendations

From the foregoing, we realized and found it necessary that distinguishing Zakāt from Ṣadaqat is the best option for Muslims in Ogun State, if truly we look forward to a society free of poverty, wealth inequality, economic instability, fear of unknown and enmity, social insecurity and moral decadency. These are targeted by the Sharī'ah to be eradicated for the well-being of entire mankind through the institution of Zakāt. The following are hereby suggested:

1. Introduction of Zakāt refreshing seminars and trainings for Imams: It is obvious that having a large number of Imams and scholars in Ogun State, those equipped with adequate knowledge about Zakāt are few. This has been a great hindrance towards distinguishing Zakāt from Ṣadaqat by their congregation. Therefore, it is not enough to admit that reading the Qur'an and knowledge about Ṣalāt should be the only pre-requisite for Imamship, sound knowledge about Zakāt is also very compulsory. The stakeholders of the Muslim Ummah in the state should make it a point of duty to organize training and retraining programmes for Imams from one community to another. This should be the sole responsibility of the League of Imams and Alfas in the State.

2. Public enlightenment and sensitization on Zakāt: Muslim Scholars should endeavour to preach the beauty in paying Zakāt, distinguish it from Ṣadaqat and state its benefits to individuals and society at large. The sensitization on Zakāt to the Muslims

should go beyond Mimbar. Public lectures should also serve as an avenue where at least a five to 10-minute talk should be dedicated to Zakāt as being done by Naṣrul-Jahi-l-Fātih Society (NAṢFAT) for its congregation. Muslim scholars should improve their Da'wah methodology and devise tactical means of capturing the hearts of the rich Muslims towards showing mercy to the less privileged and also contributing to the development of society with their wealth. Admonition with good methodology would soften their hearts: "Invite to the way of your Lord with wisdom and good instruction..." (Q16V125). Periodic lectures after morning (Ṣubh) or evening (Ishāi) obligatory Ṣalāt is another easy means of reaching out to a relatively reasonable number of Muslims.

At this juncture, it is found worthy to suggest that other Islamic organizations should also make use of media like television and radio to educate Muslims, as it has been packaged by Zakāt and Ṣadaqat Foundation to have weekly radio enlightenment program, purposely for Muslims to be informed about how, when, and what to be given out as Zakāt. This eventually would assist the majority of the Muslims to understand the position of Ṣadaqat away from Zakāt.

3. Grassroots Zakāt and Ṣadaqat agencies: There is a need to found more agencies for Zakāt and Ṣadaqat at the grassroots level. Most of our well-to-do Muslims in the rural areas are not aware of how to pay Zakāt. This is where we have farmers who are involved in a relatively large scale or commercial agriculture, yet they don't pay Zakāt during harvest. All they do is just dash out some of the produce to their mosque Imams and count it as Zakāt. Eventually, the Imams don't bother about preaching Zakāt, once the portion received is sufficient for him and his family. Establishing more Zakāt and Ṣadaqat agencies at the local level would go a long way in keeping the faithful Muslims informed, and through this, they know the differences between the two concepts (Zakāt & Ṣadaqat).

These grassroots agencies would be there to assist the community Imams in educating the Muslims. Akanni (2006) suggested the formation of what he called the Zakāt Trust Fund and outlined activities to be followed which include: designing Zakāt collection forms, determining and publicizing the niṣāb of each relevant item for Zakāt, requesting for the affordable month of the year to pay Zakāt by eligible payers, Zakāt payers are to pay directly to the bank account(s) run by the organization(s) design forms for beneficiaries with conditions that make someone eligible, and set a day aside for presentation to the beneficiaries in the public with other programmes to make it colourful. We also add that, Ṣadaqat should also be given attention separately with periodic collection and distribution of likes of food items, used clothes, second-hand household appliances, and giving tokens to the needy. This would formalize awareness of the differences between the two concepts. It is agreed that all the grassroots agencies for Zakāt and those in the city should follow all the processes highlighted in this and that of Akanni's work.

4. Motivation: It is strongly suggested that those who out of faithfulness and sincerity pay Zakāt should be motivated. This should be done through transparent and judicious disbursement of money collected by the existing Islamic organizations that take it as a responsibility. Some of these organizations run the same bank account for both Zakāt and Ṣadaqat, except NAṢFAT Agency for Zakāt and Ṣadaqat (NAZAS) which separates the latter from the former. Those who have been paying are yet to see true administration and

management of the funds. In addition, there is suspicion that some scholars collect the Zakāt from these wealthy people to enrich themselves, therefore, discouraging the payers and reducing what they give out, which would eventually not be enough to be called Zakāt but Şadaqat. In addition, it is part of the motivation to pray for the Zakāt payers during the disbursement ceremony. Praying for them is relevant with Q9V103, as this will by Allah's grace cleanse them and increase their wealth.

5. Government intervention: The government should make it part of its responsibility to encourage the payment of Zakāt as a way of moving humanity forward. This should be surrounded by accountability in the administration and distribution. The opinion of Muhammad Maidoki (2022) is quite accepted; "...just like Sukuk that is now redefining the infrastructural development in Nigeria, Zakāt also has the potential to reposition the country's economy as it will in turn bring many Nigerians out of poverty." He mentioned this at a workshop themed: "Maximizing the Power of Zakāt to support families forced to flee in Nigeria" organized by the United Nations High Commission for the Refugees (UNHCR) in Abuja. This implies that the government in Ogun State in collaboration with grounded Islamic scholars in the aspect of Zakāt technicality can as well put in place a legalized framework for its collection and disbursement in the state, as it is been practiced in most states in the northern part of the country. In fact, with this practice, well-meaning Muslims will publicly distinguish Şadaqat from Zakāt, as it will be well stated in the legislation that will establish such.

Conclusion

This paper within its objectives has explained the meaning of Zakāt and Şadaqat with their differences in terms and conditions. The technical know-how that surrounds Zakāt like other pillars of Islam has out-rightly nullified misrepresenting it with Şadaqat. Therefore, such practice in Ogun State as far as Zakāt is concerned is devoid of its establishment in Sharī'ah. However, little knowledge; insensitivity of some Muslim scholars and Imams; insincerity on the part of some wealthy Muslims; insufficient agencies to manage the collection and disbursement, and insufficient publicity led to the misrepresentation of Zakāt to Şadaqat in Ogun State.

Hopefully, the suggestion in this work, if followed, would not only assist in improving the payment of Zakāt in Ogun State but also serve as a guide towards separating the act of giving Zakāt and Şadaqat without misplacement or misrepresentation.

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